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Perceived Influence of Single Parenting on Academic Performance of Social Studies Upper Basic II Students in Gwer West, Benue State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the perceived influence of single parenting on academic performance of Social Studies Upper basic II students in Gwer West local government of Benue State. Two research objectives and two research questions guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design and the population comprised of 5,874 Social Studies Upper basic II students across 12 government owned and grant-aided schools. The sample of the study consisted of 588 students from the selected schools using random sampling. The study used Single Parenting and Academic Performance Questionnaire (SPAPQ) to collect data with its face, content and construct validity done by two experts with reliability coefficients of 0.70 using Cronbach Alpha. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions. Findings indicated that single parenting has influence on time management and assignment completion on Social Studies Upper basic II students in Gwer West local government of Benue State. It was recommended among others that, single parents should monitor their children, and ensure that they have a study timetable and strictly adhered to it.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Assignment Completion, Single Parenting, Time Management, Social Studies

INTRODUCTION

Education is the most important thing to have for the betterment of the entire society as it holds enormous influence and potentials on the quality of life of individuals. Education develops confidence and helps to build the personality of a person. Agogo et al. (2018) opines that education is expected to develop the mental and social skills as well as competencies for an individual to live and contribute to the development of the society. Education is said to be the bedrock of an individual giving rise to national development. Oganwu (2014) as cited in Agba (2024) maintains that dynamism in education is what led to the introduction of Social Studies in the school curriculum as a discipline soon after World War II.

Social Studies is a field of study that focuses on the interconnectedness of human societies and their interactions across time and space. Garba (2021) sees Social Studies as a problem solving discipline designed to assist man proffer solutions to his problems whether, cultural, geographical, sociological, historical, political and psychological. Other important skills are map reading, and interpretation. Social Studies is an academic discipline that brings the realities of life to the learners by inculcating into them the relevant knowledge, attitudes, skills and values that would make them responsible and disciplined members of the society (Utulu, 2013). It encompasses a wide range of disciplines such as History, Geography, Economics, Political Science, Government, Civic Education, Sociology, Psychology, Anthropology etc.

Social studies emphasizes how a citizen is to be educated and made functional. This is because these generations of people are not only intellectually capable, but are practically oriented and be able to think for themselves (Gbinde et al, 2023). Social Studies is therefore, made a compulsory subject for both primary and junior secondary schools. It is intended to develop competencies required for solving man's diverse environmental problems for better and effective social living. Agba (2024) opines that, the focus of Social Studies is to extricate the Nigerian child from the apron strings of colonial education which merely propagated foreign values. The teaching of Social Studies is geared towards building a verily Nigerian nation irrespective of ethnic diversity. It is also directed towards equipping learners with functional knowledge, attitudes, skills, and values; and the success of all that is taught and learnt through Social Studies education is measured through academic performance of students.

Academic performance is a concept encompassing the outcome of educational goals, often measured by grades, test scores, and other formal assessments. For example, the academic performance of a student in Social Studies includes observable and measurable behaviour of a student at any point in time during a course. According to Gbinde et al. (2023) in Social Studies, student's academic performance consists of their scores at any particular time obtained from a teacher-made test. It is the ability of the student to study and remember facts and being able to communicate his knowledge orally or in written form even in an examination condition. Khaliq et al. (2020) sees academic performance as the ability of students to manage their studies and the various tasks assigned by their teachers, including the capability to study, retain information and convey acquired knowledge verbally or in written form. It reflects various cognitive, emotional, social, and behavioral aspects of a student's life and is influenced by a multitude of factors including family background, socioeconomic status, family systems (single or dual parenting), parenting styles among others. Mrinde (2014) avers that family systems like single parenting influence various aspects of the academic performance of students including time management and assignment completion.

Single parenting is a social phenomenon that has come to stay in human society. It refers to a situation by which a person brings up a child or children without a partner. Nwiro (2014) sees single parenting as a situation where there is only one parent and one or more children living together in a home. It involves one parent, either mother or father, being solely responsible for raising their children without the help of the other parent. This situation can arise due to various factors such as divorce, separation, death of a spouse, or single parenthood by choice. Single parents often face unique challenges, including the need to fulfill dual roles of both parents, managing financial responsibilities, and addressing the emotional and psychological well-being of their children. Muslihat and Listiana (2021) asserts that single mothers are more likely to experience higher levels of stress and financial difficulties compared to single fathers and children in single-parent families may face issues related to behavioral and emotional development, which may affect their time management.

Time management in the context of students can be defined as the ability to effectively organize and plan how much time to spend on specific activities. This skill is crucial for students as it influences their academic performance and overall productivity. According to Razali et al. (2018), time management involves several factors such as time planning, time attitudes, and avoidance of time-wasting activities. Effective time management enables students to balance their academic responsibilities with other aspects of their lives, leading to improved academic outcomes. Similarly, Aduke (2015) opines that time management is a set of practices that work together to help individuals get more value out of their time, aiming to improve the quality of life. For students, this means prioritizing tasks, avoiding procrastination, and effectively scheduling study time to enhance on time completion of assignment which lead to academic success.

Assignment completion refers to the process by which students complete their assigned tasks and submit them within the stipulated deadlines. This concept is closely tied to students' ability to manage their time and stay organized. Suamuang et al. (2021) asserts that assignment completion is influenced by various factors including task orientation, cooperation, teacher feedback, and time management. Effective assignment completion involves not only finishing tasks on time but also ensuring the quality and

accuracy of the work submitted. Pechová et al. (2023) noted that assignment can vary in format, including essays, research projects, problem-solving tasks, and practical activities. Their effectiveness in enhancing learning outcomes is influenced by clear instructions, relevance to the curriculum, and timely feedback from educators.

Theoretical Framework

The study is hinged on the Social Learning Theory by Albert Bandura (1977) which posits that, learning occurs through observation, imitation, and modeling, emphasizing the role of environmental and cognitive factors in shaping behavior. The theory's central assumption is that individuals, especially children, do not learn solely through direct experience but by watching others referred to as models and observing the consequences of their actions. Bandura identified four key processes in social learning: “attention” (noticing the behavior), “retention” (remembering it), “reproduction” (ability to replicate it), and “motivation” (having the desire to imitate, influenced by rewards or punishments).

This theory has significant implications for understanding child development within the context of single parenting. In single-parent households, the child often has fewer adult models to observe, potentially limiting the diversity of social behaviors and coping mechanisms they are exposed to. The single parent's behavior becomes highly influential, as the child may model their emotional responses, stress management techniques, and social interactions based on this singular example. If the parent demonstrates resilience, positive communication, and constructive problem-solving, the child is more likely to adopt these traits.

Empirically, Ngwoke et al. (2013) investigated the effect of time management on academic adjustment of deviant in-school adolescents and single parents' students in Eastern Senatorial Zone of Kogi State, and found that time management training technique significantly enhanced the academic adjustment of deviant in-school and single parent students. Kim (2021) examined the transition from a two-parent to a single-parent household and child development, and discovered that students transitioning from a two-parent to a single-parent household exhibited an 8.5% decline in their ability to manage academic time effectively. This decline is often attributed to the lack of parental supervision and support that dual-parent households typically provide. Furthermore, Etodike (2020) investigated effect of time management and monetary rewards on cognitive task accomplishment among students of Nnamdi Azikiwe secondary school, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria and found that students with better time management skills tend to perform better academically, indicating that single-parent students might face additional challenges in achieving academic success due to poor time management.

Olufemi (2014) investigated the effect of assignment on mathematics achievement of secondary school students in south west Nigeria, and findings revealed that there was a significant difference between the academic performance of students exposed to assignment completion and those not exposed to assignment completion. Anyakoha (2016) examined single parenting as correlate of academic performance of students in unity secondary school in South East Geo-Political Zone in Nigeria, and found that single parents, despite their financial struggles, support their children's education, yet their involvement does not equate to higher academic performance due to the lack of consistent supervision and emotional support. From the fore-going investigations, it can be deduced that all the reviewed empirical studies are related to this study on single parenting in the aspect of time management and assignment completion on academic performance of Social Studies Upper basic II students. However, the studies are different because none has been done geographically in Gwer West local government area of Benue State.

Statement of the Problem

While there is a growing body of research on the impact of single parenting on academic performance, studies specifically focused on the context of Gwer West LGA are limited. This research gap highlights the need for a deeper understanding of the unique challenges faced by single-parent families in this region and the specific implications for the academic performance of Social Studies students. Based on the researchers observation, poor academic performance of students in Nigeria education system seems to be

attributed to educationists, politicians and the government. Sometimes, teachers are the first to be accused when there is a fall in academic standard while nothing or very little is said about other factors such as single parenting, time management, and assignment completion. It is worthy to note that, while some students perform highly and others do not perform well, they are concerns about those who do not perform well because if this poor performance goes unchecked, the secondary schools may lose their reputation, which could result in loss of confidence in their secondary school graduates.

However, single parenting has increased drastically and this trend has the possibility of depriving many school children the opportunity to make better academic performance. By exploring this topic, researchers can contribute to evidence-based interventions and policies aimed at supporting the academic and social-emotional development of children from single-parent households in Gwer West local government area and similar contexts. It is against this background that the researcher deems it necessary to investigate the perceived influence of single parenting on academic performance of Social Studies Upper basic II students in Gwer West local government area of Benue State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. ascertain the perceived influence of single parenting on time management of Social Studies Upper basic II students in Gwer West local government area of Benue State.
2. examine the perceived influence of single parenting on assignment completion of Social Studies Upper basic II students.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the perceived influence of single parenting on time management of Social Studies upper basic II students in Gwer West local government area of Benue State?
2. What is the perceived influence of single parenting on assignment completion of Social Studies upper basic II students?

METHOD

This study employed descriptive survey design. According to Emaikwu (2019), this method helps the researcher to explain the variables in the study on the basis of information gathered from the respondents. The population of the study comprised 5,874 Social Studies Upper basic II students in Gwer West local government area of Benue State. Sample size of 588 secondary school students across 12 governments owned and grant-aided schools were selected using random sampling. Single Parenting and Academic Performance Questionnaire (SPAPQ) was administered to gather data for the study.

The instrument was validated by two experts; one each in Social Studies Education and Measurement and Evaluation all in the Faculty of Education, Benue State University, Makurdi. The validators were requested to look at the purpose of the study and ascertain if the items are valid, examine the language used, the comprehensiveness of the instrument and the adequacy of the instrument to elicit responses from the respondents and as such make suggestions for improvement for each subject and structure item. A trial testing of the instruments were carried out on 20 upper basic II students in the area of study. The reliability coefficient of SPAPQ was computed using Cronbach Alpha which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.70. The instruments were made up of 2 main sections of A and B. Section A contained information about the questionnaire options and instructions, while section B was made up of the items to be responded to, and contained 10 items having a 4-point modified Likert Scale with options ranging from Strongly Agree (SA)-4, Agree (A)-3, Disagree (D)-2 and Strongly Disagree (SD)-1. The decision for accepting whether single parenting has significant influence on academic performance of students was based on $4+3+2+1=10$ divide by 4 which is 2.50. The respondents were to tick appropriately the options that best described their opinions.

Data were collected using the help of 12 research assistants who were teachers in the sampled schools. They were briefed on the procedure for administration of the instrument for one hour in order to help administer copies of the instrument to the students. The areas where the instrument was not clear were explained. The researcher appealed for cooperation on the ground that the information given would be used purely for research work. To determine the accurate return of the instrument, the researcher

administered the instrument and collected at the spot. The mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions, 2.50 level of significance were used as the critical mean for decision making on the item responded to, and below 2.50 was considered negative.

RESULTS

The results of the study are presented, analyzed and interpreted according to the research questions.

Table 1: Mean Influence of Single Parenting on Time Management of Social Studies Upper basic II Students

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	My single parent's busy schedule affects my ability to manage my study time	161	277	80	70	2.90	.937	Accepted
2	I often struggle to prioritize my tasks due to the lack of guidance from both parents.	334	184	30	40	3.30	.864	Accepted
3	The absence of one parent affects my ability to create study schedule.	259	249	55	25	3.26	.798	Accepted
4	I find it challenging to manage my study time due to the financial constraints faced by my single parent.	182	301	65	40	3.06	.830	Accepted
5	My single parent's emotional support helps me stay motivated to manage my study time.	196	242	100	50	2.99	.919	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation					3.102	.8696	Accepted	

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 1 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 1 to 5 are 2.90, 3.30, 3.26, 3.06, and 2.99 with corresponding standard deviations of .937, .864, .798, .830, and .919 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.102 with the cluster standard deviation of .8696 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that single parenting has influence on time management among Social Studies Upper basic II students in Gwer West local government area of Benue State.

Table 2: Mean Influence of Single Parenting on Assignment Completion of Social Studies Upper basic II Students

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	I often receive feedback from my single parent on my assignment submissions which helps me improve.	488	75	25	0	3.79	.503	Accepted

The finding is in nexus with Kim (2021) who found that, students transitioning from a two-parent to a single-parent household exhibited an 8.5% decline in their ability to manage academic time effectively. This decline is often attributed to the lack of parental supervision and support that dual-parent households typically provide. Similarly, Etodike (2020) found that students with better time management skills tend to perform better academically, indicating that single-parent students might face additional challenges in achieving academic success due to poor time management.

The study also revealed that single parenting has influence on assignment completion among Social Studies Upper basic II students in Gwer West local government area of Benue State. This means that single parents do not spend adequate time with their children that could enable them assist in making sure their assignments are done. This finding concurs with Olufemi (2014) who found that there was a significant difference between the academic performance of students exposed to assignment and those not

exposed to assignment. This finding also corroborates with Anyakoha (2016) who found that single parents, despite their financial struggles, support their children's education, yet their involvement does not equate to higher academic performance due to the lack of consistent supervision and emotional support. Single-parent students may face societal perceptions and emotional stress, which can further hinder their academic engagement and completion of assignments.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that single parenting has influence on time management and assignment completion among Social Studies Upper basic II students in Gwer West local government area of Benue State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Single parents should monitor their children and ensure that they have a study time table and strictly adhere to it.
2. Single parents should involve themselves in helping their children to complete their assignments and home works. They (parents) can help to explain difficult aspects of assignments to their children.

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